

CSC: Collaborative System Configuration for I/O-Intensive Applications in Multi-Tenant Clouds

Supplementary materials for rebuttal

pap136s2

1 (Reviewer 1) Evaluations on Applications Mixes

We evaluate the effectiveness of CSC when the number of co-located VMs increases. We first co-locate three VMs that host different applications. In this case, there are $3 \times 5 = 15$ parameters to be tuned, and $C_5^3 = 10$ different mixes of applications in total. The total I/O bandwidth is limited to 450MB/s.

Figure 1: The normalized execution time of each application with CSC. Three VMs are co-located.

Fig. 1 shows the execution time of each application when running with CSC. The execution time is normalized to the baseline (fair bandwidth allocation, as described in Section VII.A). The x-axis shows the application mixes (e.g., "N+S+W" represents the mix of *Nutch indexing*, *Sort* and *DFSIO-Write*). As we can observe, **no application gets worse performance compared to the baseline, while the performance of the applications is improved by 7.25% on average (up to 18.55%)**.

Figure 2: The normalized execution time of each application with CSC. Four VMs are co-located.

We also try co-locating four VMs. There are 20 parameters to be tuned and $C_5^4 = 4$ different mixes of applications in total. The total I/O bandwidth is limited to 600MB/s. As shown in Fig. 2, **the performance of the applications is improved by 6.65% on average (up to 17.76%), while no application gets worse performance compared to the baseline.**

2 (Reviewer 2) I/O Hierarchy in Linux Kernel

Figure 3: The I/O hierarchy in Linux Kernel.

In this work, HDFS (3.3.1) is the file system used in the experiments. In fact, **CSC can cooperate with file systems that have different implementations.**

Fig. 3 shows the I/O hierarchy in the Linux kernel. Generally, the user application uses the system call (*read* or *write*) to read or write the file on the I/O device. The system call goes through the virtual file system (VFS), the file system (e.g., Ext4), *page cache*, generic block layer and I/O scheduler layer, and

reach the I/O device.

When the read/write characteristics changes (caused by user application) or the available I/O bandwidth changes (caused by the adjustment of hardware resources), the *Optimizer* (Section VI) in CSC finds the appropriate parameters of the *page cache* in order to make it work effectively. CSC does not rely on any assumption about the file system.

References

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